

Automated Steel Surface Defect Detection using Optimized Cascaded CaffeNet region Network

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Abstract: Only a small number of low-resolution images are available to address the fundamental difficulties in defect detection during steel sheet manufacture, which results in less than ideal recognition accuracy and overall deep learning algorithm performance. A deep learning-based approach for detecting steel surface flaws is described in this paper. A new Optimized Cascaded CaffeNetRegion Network (OCAFRN) is utilized to detect defects from surveillance cameras by utilizing vision machine technology. By mapping the features using R-CNN and the Electric Fish Optimization Approach (EFOA), this cascaded structure with a 3D CaffeNet is utilized to extract the region of the steel sheets with faults. It outperforms the other standard algorithms in terms of recognition accuracy, which is consistent and comprehensive for both positive and negative categories under a variety of scenarios. In contrast, OCAFRN, which is an improved network model, exhibits optimal performance for smaller image models, achieving 96.5% of defect detection accuracy with a reduction in 3.2% of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) in comparison with the existing methods like Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Back Propagation Algorithm (BPA) and Radial Basis Function Network (RBF).

Keywords: accuracy, CaffeNet, defect detection, electric fish optimization, steel sheets

1. Introduction

Imperfections like scratches, holes, scars, cracks, and protrusions can affect the quality and functionality of steel products, stemming from the complexities of the steel manufacturing process¹. Ensuring the manufacturing of high-quality steel requires the detection and correction of these flaws. A variety of approaches, such as automated methods including machine learning, manual inspection, and non-destructive testing, are used to identify surface defects in steel. As object detection has advanced quickly, deep learning techniques—especially those that use Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)—have become more popular in international research².

Han et al¹., improved the Faster R-CNN algorithm by integrating VGG-16 as the backbone network and implementing two cascaded detection networks for feature fusion, achieving a detection accuracy of 98.29% and a speed of 12.26 fps on a steel defect dataset. Similarly, Wang et al³., applied Faster R-CNN with ResNet101 and

transfer learning to detect surface defects in steel strips, achieving high precision, recall rates, and swift detection performance. To enhance flaw detection efficiency in hot-rolled strip steel, Liu et al. utilized SSD combined with ResNet and a channel attention mechanism, enabling faster and more streamlined defect identification⁴. Akhyar et al. demonstrated the effectiveness of ResNet in detecting surface defects on steel plates with high precision and speed. Furthermore, Liu et al. introduced an enhanced R-Tiny-YOLO v3, incorporating residual networks and SPP modules, optimized for embedded systems⁵. Although these algorithms perform well on medium- to high-resolution images, they face difficulties with low-resolution images, leading to reduced accuracy in complex scenes with overlapping defects⁶. The research highlights include

- Defect detection during online manufacturing of steel sheets
- Feature extraction using Faster RCNN, CAFFENET, OCAFRN

- Classification of defects using R-CNN, HYBRID KNN, SVM
- Optimal accuracy rate achieved for classification

2. Related Work

The two main types of deep learning-based target detection algorithms are single-stage algorithms that carry out position regression directly and two-stage techniques. Typical two-stage algorithms that follow a sequential approach are R-CNN⁶, Fast R-CNN⁷, and Faster R-CNN⁸. This entails creating candidate boxes for regions, taking elements out of each box, and forecasting the categories that belong with them.

On the other hand, single-stage algorithms are ideal for real-time applications since they offer a notable speedup in detection. For example, the SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector) developed by Liu et al.⁹ is faster than the Faster R-CNN. ResNet¹⁰ combines Focal Loss with a feature pyramid network to solve sample imbalance in single-stage detection. A fully convolutional neural network YOLOv1¹¹ delivers fast speed, but accuracy may be compromised, and it may have trouble anticipating the number of objects.

With several upgrades since its creation, the YOLO framework has produced ever better models, including YOLOv2¹², YOLOv3¹³, YOLOv4¹⁴, and so on. The main factor in the YOLO series' broad popularity was its modular programming YOLOv5¹⁵, which was made possible by very good encapsulation that made it easy to use. Inspired by the SimOTA approach of YOLOX¹⁷, YOLOv7¹⁶ incorporates cutting-edge technologies like model scaling, auxiliary head detection, re-parameterized convolutions, and effective aggregation networks. The decoupled heads from YOLOX are introduced in YOLOv8¹⁹, an improvement on YOLOv5, which separates the classification and regression operations. Instead of using an anchor-based architecture, the model uses an anchor-free design and uses DFL Loss + CIoU Loss for regression and BCE Loss for classification. Mosaic data augmentation is turned off in the last 10 rounds using a task-aligned allocator sample method to improve accuracy. It is possible to describe YOLO as an algorithmic framework that is largely focused on industrial deployment¹⁸.

Single-stage and two-stage algorithms for object detection make predictions based on presumptions. Unlike single-stage algorithms that rely on anchors or target centroids, two-stage techniques use intermediate proposal boxes. These presumptions are intimately related to the algorithmic performance.

In 2020, Carion et al.¹⁸ presented DETR, a transformation-based set-based object detection system that does not require post-processing steps like NMS. Due to its change in global modeling capabilities, DETR is excellent at

recognizing larger items; but, it performs less well for tiny objects since it lacks multi-scale features, feature pyramids, and complex detection heads. Dynamic anchor boxes were first presented by DAB-DETR¹⁹ in 2022, DN-DETR²⁰ expedited training, and DINO enhanced both. Group-based one-to-many assignment was introduced in Group-DETR²¹; light weighting of the model was the goal of Lite-DETR²². Baidu's RT-DETR²³ accomplished real-time detection, outperforming other algorithms, such as YOLO, in terms of accuracy on the COCO dataset²⁴.

Practical applications in the industrial arena continue to favor the YOLO series notwithstanding DETR's improvements. By utilizing a variety of training methods and a CNN environment that is compatible with hardware, YOLO continues to be a leader. In contrast to the established industrial framework YOLO, the DETR and RCNN series are used in academics to validate new modules, enhancements, and optimizations. Particularly on industrial datasets, YOLO-based object recognition has continuously improved. The algorithms YOLOv5 and YOLOv7 tackle difficulties in steel surface flaw detection. Enhanced recently by Guo et al.²⁵ and Wang et al.²⁶. These highlight ongoing efforts to improve YOLO-based algorithms for steel surface defect detection, addressing challenges such as randomness and overlapping defects²⁷. The study uses advanced architectures to solve the algorithms in circumstances with overlapping defects and lower-resolution images²⁸. It integrates the feature fusion technique and presents the convolutional module made for low-resolution pictures. Decoupled heads from YOLOX are used in the detection procedure, improving capabilities with the efficient attention mechanism²⁹. This method is appropriate for real-world use in production settings and a low parameter count. The network structure is shown in Figure 1.

The instrument used for inspecting the quality of planar materials for defect identification by automated visual introspection plays an important role for classifying the defects which is a crucial task involved in online quality inspection of steel sheets³⁰. Manufacturing steel sheets in the form of flattened structures is a highly cumbersome process because of the diversified shape and structure of the steels sheets and also existing ambiguity in the within-class and between-class similarity measures³¹. Industrial revolution has enabled computer vision based automation in monitoring the quality of fabricated hot and cold rolled steel sheets. For this purpose, image processing algorithms are implemented consisting of 5 steps, namely, the acquiring the images of steel sheets, noise removal, feature extrusion and reduction, followed by a classifier for defect classification³². Future work in this domain will suggest suitable methods for enhancing the quality inspection of steel sheet fabrication²³.

Vision based defect detection is an essential step in quality steel sheet manufacturing. For this purpose, machine

learning algorithms are currently deployed. Still today, many of the steel fabricating industries use manual inspection by naked eyes which require time for the skilled worker to be trained with the job. Also this manual inspection is prone to errors²⁴). The technology behind automatic defect detection in steel sheet fabrication is a cost effective method with a feedback mechanism for quality control in no matter of time. Gathering the data set required for image segmentation and detection of steel sheets is an expensive method. Transfer learning based U-Net (TLU-Net) is used by the researchers for defect identification from the images of the steel sheets²⁵). Two types of framework, like ResNet and DenseNet are used here. Performance comparison is carried out between these two frame work to identify an accurate classifier²⁶). Researchers have proved that nearly 26% increase in classification is achieved by using TLU-Net as compared with random methods.

Quality assurance has created an increase in quality manufacturing of steel sheets through computer aided diagnosis for flaw detection on the flat surface of the steel sheets. The statistical and spectral features are used as inputs to train the machine learning model for detection of quality of the steel sheets. To ensure quality fabrication, deep learning methods are used. Convolutional neural networks (CNN) with Xception framework²⁷) is used by the researchers for detecting the flaws in steel sheets from hyper-spectral images captured by high resolution cameras with an accuracy of 94%.

Steel defects are a frequent problem in steel companies. Proper quality control can reduce quality problems arising from steel defects. Nowadays, steel defects can detect by automation methods that utilize certain algorithms. Deep learning can help the steel defect detection algorithm become more sophisticated. In this study, we use deep learning CNN with Xception architecture to detect steel defects from images taken from high-frequency and high-resolution cameras. There are two techniques used, and both produce respectively 0.94% and 0.85% accuracy. The Xception architecture used in this case shows optimal and stable performance in the process and its results³⁰).

Conventional methods are less accurate with less speed in quality control of steel sheets. ResNet50 and Faster R-CNN are used to reduce the running time. Deformable convolution network (DCN) is used to overcome this problem with a detection efficiency of 98% approximately²⁸). Researchers have also used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Self-Organizing Maps (SOM) for computer aided diagnosis of steel sheet defects during fabrication. YOLO-v5 is also used by the industrialists for real time steel surface defect detection with an efficacy of 72% only²⁹). Hence by comparing the above methods, it is decided to use CaffeNet, because of the expressive framework, execution speed and modularity³¹).

3. Proposed methodology

The resolution of the captured steel sheet images is mostly determined by the type of the vision sensor employed and it's positioning in the industrial area for monitoring purpose. The aforementioned factors encompass the process of change in detection through the use of images, including atmospheric conditions, geographical, temporal, spectral, and thematic limitations, soil moisture conditions, and radiometric resolution. Preprocessing is employed to select the pertinent data, while change detection techniques can be employed to mitigate the potential impact of satellite data. The features are extracted using the CaffeNet model³²). Subsequently, the faster region-based convolutional network (faster R-CNN) has demonstrated exceptional performance in object detection. Subsequently, a learning approach based on Electric Fish Optimization is presented to optimize both the classifier and loss function of OCAFRN. The model under consideration is depicted in Figure 1.

3.1. Preprocessing

The task of 3-dimensional classification has a greater level of difficulty in terms of visualization compared to 2-dimensional and 1-dimensional classification problems, as the latter two may be easily represented in a simplified 2-dimensional space. The concept is illustrated in accompanying graphic, wherein a three-dimensional feature space is partitioned into two distinct two-dimensional feature spaces³³). If a subsequent discovery reveals an association between the two feature spaces, it may be feasible to further reduce the number of features. In addition, the reduction of feature dimensions in the data collection facilitates expedited data visualization process eliminates extraneous sounds and superfluous characteristics. The utilization of the low variance filter and high correlation filter is employed as a means of reducing dimensionality³⁴).

Fig.1: Overall architecture of the proposed steel sheets defect detection

The low variance filter has been utilized as an edge-detection technique and has demonstrated its effectiveness

in comparison to other methods, which can be employed as a dimension reduction method. The variance filter is utilized to compute the local similarity within an image, with a specific emphasis on abrupt alterations in the brightness of the image. The low variance filter possesses the capability to identify regions that exhibit minimal variation among their constituent elements, utilizing a combination of variance and threshold analysis. This implies that, depending on the specified input threshold, the filter demonstrates efficacy in identifying and diminishing less significant components within the dataset, such as the image background³⁵. Simultaneously, it retains crucial information, such as the image edges. This characteristic suggests that the filter may yield favorable outcomes when employed in conjunction with feature extraction techniques that focus on edge detection, such as the orthogonal wavelet transform. Assuming a matrix of dimensions p by p , it is possible to choose omit a subset of the data in order to compute its variance. Equation (1) provides the calculation for the variance of the provided set as below,

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{i=1}^p (x_i - \hat{x})^2 \tag{1}$$

where 'd' is the relationship of the set of pixels, 'x' denotes the value of the $i - th$ pixel, and 'x' represents the arithmetic mean of the pixel values inside the specified set. Correlation filtering is a highly effective technique for object recognition due to its inherent capability to concurrently execute two fundamental tasks. In this approach, the variables exhibiting a strong association are identified, and then, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is employed to select a single variable. Variables with higher values of VIF more than 5 can be eliminated³⁶.

3.2. Feature Extraction

In the context of aerial scene categorization, the attainment of accurate results heavily relies on the implementation of effective feature extraction techniques. In addition to conventional techniques that involve manual feature engineering, there has been a significant advancement in the field of deep learning with the introduction of deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs). These CNN-based approaches have demonstrated remarkable performance in recent times. One of the commonly utilized convolutional neural network (CNN) models is CaffeNet³⁷.

The Caffe library is well recognized as a prominent tool for deep learning, with a special emphasis on convolutional neural networks. The software has been developed by the Berkeley Vision and Learning Centre (BVLC) in collaboration with community contributions. Caffe offers a high degree of customization through its configuration files, allowing users to tailor the software to their own needs. Additionally, it supports seamless extension with new layer types, enabling users to incorporate novel

functionalities. Furthermore, Caffe boasts a highly efficient Convolutional Neural Network (ConvNet) implementation, ensuring rapid processing of data. This also applies to the method described, where feature vectors are taken from CaffeNet and pre-trained on Imagenet³⁸. The architecture of CaffeNet closely resembles that of AlexNet, albeit with notable distinctions. Firstly, CaffeNet does not employ relighting data-augmentation during training. Secondly, there is a reversal in the sequence of pooling and normalization layers, with pooling being performed prior to normalization in CaffeNet³⁹. It is comprised of a total of five convolutional layers and three fully linked layers. The dimensions of the input for CaffeNet are 227×227 pixels, with three channels representing the red, green, and blue colour as in Figure 2.

Fig.2: Architecture of CaffeNet

3.3. Feature Mapping Extraction

Furthermore, in an effort to enhance the feature representation capabilities of the backbone network, we employed Electric Fish search optimization on the backbone network utilized for feature extraction in Faster R-CNN. This approach facilitated the generation of an ideal cross-layer connection, hence enabling more efficient feature extraction. Subsequently, an enhanced Oceanic and Atmospheric Carbon Flux Research Network (OCAFRN) is formulated with the objective of broadening the scope of OCAFRN's exploration capabilities. The task of obtaining the most suitable parameter values for OCAFRN is a challenge that falls under the category of non-deterministic polynomial-time hard problems. This type of problem can be effectively addressed by employing swarm intelligence techniques. Subsequently, a novel learning technique based on Electric Fish search optimization is proposed to enhance the optimization of the classifier and loss function in the OCAFRN model. Furthermore, the support vector machine (SVM) approach is utilized to augment the classifier's capacity for learning⁴⁰.

The Faster R-CNN approach is considered a cutting-edge technique for object detection. This part provides an introduction to fundamental information. The convolutional characteristics of the image are subjected to processing by the Region Proposal Network (RPN). Subsequently, the generation of region proposals occurs as the output of the Region Proposal Network (RPN). Additionally, the object score is calculated for every region

suggestion. Reference region recommendations are generated by applying a sliding window to the output features of the top-level convolutional layer. Hence, the determination of the quality of region proposals is contingent upon the top-level characteristics. Specifically, these characteristics are transmitted to the box-regression layer (reg) and the box-classification layer (cls) for information processing. To clarify, the structure of Reverse Polish Notation (RPN) is implemented through the use of a convolutional layer with dimensions $n \times n$, as well as two additional convolutional layers with dimensions 1×1 .

At every sliding window location, multiple area ideas are concurrently anticipated. It is assumed that the number of suggestions for each site is limited to a maximum value denoted as k . Hence, the outputs of the $4k$ -regression layer encode the positional coordinates of k rectangle proposals, while the cls layer outputs $2k$ scores. Specifically, the likelihood of an object or the absence of an object for each proposition is determined through the calculation of individual scores. Additionally, the positioning of an anchor is determined by the size and aspect ratio. The anchor is positioned at the centre of the sliding window, as shown in Figure 1. It is assumed that the dimensions of a convolutional feature map are denoted as $W \times H$. Consequently, the total count of anchors can be calculated as WHk . The anchor-based approach is constructed on a pyramid of anchors to reduce computational expenses. Multiple scales and aspect ratios are employed for classification and bounding box regression. The mathematical representation of the loss function in the Region Proposal Network (RPN) is denoted.

The Region Proposal Network (RPN) is trained using backpropagation (BP) and stochastic gradient descent. Backpropagation iteratively adjusts weights and biases to learn from errors, while stochastic gradient descent optimises network performance by updating parameters based on tiny, randomly selected portions of training data. The RPN uses "image-centric" training sampling to generate several positive and negative anchor boxes per image mini-batch. This method seeks to depict diverse possible interest areas. Negative samples outnumber positive ones, leaving some anchor boxes unused during network training. In training, the loss function computation uses 256 mini-batch anchor boxes. Interestingly, the number of positive examples is purposely equal to the number of negative samples, emphasizing training data balance. This technique stabilizes and improves the identification using Equations (2)-(8).

$$L_o(\{k_x\}, \{d_x\}) = \frac{1}{n_{cls}} \sum_x L_{o_{cls}}(k_x, k'_x) + \delta \frac{1}{n_{reg}} \sum_x k'_x L_{o_{reg}}(d_x, d'_x) \quad (2)$$

$$L_{o_{cls}}(k_x, k'_x) = \begin{cases} -\log k_x & \text{if } k'_x = 1 \\ -\log(1 - k_x) & \text{if } k'_x = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$L_{o_{reg}}(d_x, d'_x) = S(d_x, d'_x) \quad (4)$$

$$d_m = (m - m_i) / z_i, d_n = (n - n_i) / b_i \quad (5)$$

$$d_z = \log(z / z_i), d_b = \log(b / b_i) \quad (6)$$

$$d'_m = (m' - m_i) / z_i, d'_n = (n' - n_i) / b_i \quad (7)$$

$$d'_z = \log(z' / z_i), d'_b = \log(b' / b_i) \quad (8)$$

In the event that the quantity of positive anchor boxes falls below 128, the negative anchor boxes are employed as substitutes for the positive ones. The initialization of the layers of RPN is achieved by utilizing the pre-trained ImageNet.

Following that, the loss function parameters are optimized using the Electric Fish Optimization. To enhance the efficiency of these influential aspects, the optimization technique known as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is implemented. This work introduces the concept of utilizing the improved loss function as the fitness function. Consequently, the local and global optima are modified according to the fitness value.

These electric fields are used for a variety of purposes, including navigation, communication, and object detection. Electric fish are equipped with an electric organ that is comprised of electric disc-like cells known as electrocytes. These cells are responsible for the production of an electric field in the fish. This organ is often situated toward the base of the body, close to the tail. Electric organ discharge (EOD) is a term that is used in the scientific literature to refer to the simultaneous activation of electrocytes. The frequency and amplitude of EOD are two characteristics that define it. The time gap that occurs between each pair of successive electric signals has a direct bearing on the EOD frequency, which is inversely proportional to this time gap. Both the proximity to the stimulus (which causes a regular increase) and the existence of a novelty (which causes a sudden increase) have a significant impact on it. The amplitude of the EOD, on the other hand, is inversely related to the distance from the body surface and is proportional to the size of the fish. This is because electrocytes are added to the fish during growth, which causes their number to increase. Electro location is broken down into two groups, active and passive, depending on the EOD activity that is being investigated.

Electric fish are able to perceive their immediate environment through the fluctuations in the electric field and emit EOD when they are in an active electro area. Active electro localization has a relatively limited effective range, but it can be of great assistance to fish that live in murky or otherwise difficult surroundings in terms of locating and recognizing their prey. Through their electroreceptors, electric fish are able to detect and respond to electric signals that originate from outside sources when they are in a passive electro location. They are able to detect items at distances that are outside the range of active

electro location and communicate with other fish because the effective range of passive electro location is significantly broader. This is in contrast to active electro location, which has a much more limited range. Electric fish may sense electric currents from their conspecifics' organs or other animals in their surroundings because they are electrogenic and electroreceptive. Electric fish can also generate an electric field to communicate via electrical impulses. Electric fish can communicate numerous things. First, they can communicate their identity, gender, and socioeconomic status. Second, they may reveal physiological or motivational information. Finally, electric fish can communicate about their environment, including food and other elements. Electric fish communicate via this technology. The initialization of the population is done using the Equation (9).

$$a_{n,m} = a_{miny} + rand(a_{maxy} - a_{miny}) \tag{9}$$

where, $a_{n,m}$ is the position number y in the solution number 2 , max , and min are the maximum and minimum boundaries, respectively. Within the context of the Electric Fish Organ (EFO), similar to the natural environment, certain positions exhibit a higher frequency and employ effective electrolocation techniques, while others rely on passive electrolocation methods. The frequency value is provided within the range of the maximum and minimum values of the fitness function as indicated in Equation (10).

$$F_x^d = F_{min} + \left(\frac{Fitt_{Worst}^d - Fitt_x^d}{Fitt_{Worst}^d - Fitt_{Best}^d} \right) (F_{max} - F_{min}) \tag{10}$$

Where, F_x^d is the fitness value of the solution number x at iteration number d . $Fitt_{Worst}^d$ and $Fitt_{Best}^d$ are the worst and best obtained fitness functions values. $F_{max} - F_{min}$ are the max and min fitness functions values. The amplitude cost G_x is determined using Equation (11)

$$G_x^d \propto G_x^{d-1} (1 - \alpha) F_x^d \tag{11}$$

where, α is a value in range $[0, 1]$. The fish can only perceive prey within the biologically effective range of active electro location, which is half its size. Fish can find any nearby food source with this skill. These active electro location properties enable EFO local search or exploitation. Everyone in active mode (active electro location) moves about the search space by changing their attributes in EFO. Only one randomly selected parameter can be changed to prevent individuals from leaving the promising zone. The active range estimation is calculated using Equation (12).

$$q_x = (a_{maxy} - a_{miny}) q_x \tag{12}$$

In order to find additional solutions that are close by in the

space that is accessible, you must first estimate the distance that separates the current solution from the other options. Equation (13) is used to compute the gap that exists between the solution number x and w

$$h_{xw} = ||a_x - a_y|| = \sqrt{\sum_{y=1}^n (a_{xy} - a_{wy})^2} \tag{13}$$

Equation (14), which is used if there is at least one neighbor found in the active space; Equation (15), which is used if there is not at least one neighbor found in the active space:

$$a_{xy}^{cand} = a_{xy} + \varphi(a_{wy} - a_{xy}) \tag{14}$$

$$a_{xy}^{cand} a_{xy} \varphi q_x \tag{15}$$

where, ' w ' is a random selected solution, ' φ ' is a value between $[-1, 1]$, a_{xy}^{cand} is the position of the candidate which offers a solution of number ' x '.

In contrast to active electro location, the sensing distance is independent of the x^{th} individual and extends beyond the range observed in active electro location in natural settings. The fulfillment of the requirements of the global search or exploration mechanism of the proposed EFO algorithm is attributed to the passive electro location capability. As previously stated, the likelihood of perceiving a signal is closely correlated with both its amplitude value and the distance to the target individual. Persons in a passive state select persons in an active state who transmit electrical signals based on a probability, and subsequently alter their positions. The probability of a given solution number, denoted as x , within an active space is determined according to the Equation (16).

$$S_w = \frac{G_w/h_{xw}}{\sum_{y \in N_G} G_y/h_{xy}} \tag{16}$$

The equation (16), which is used to determine w solutions from N_G , can be solved in a variety of ways, such as by selecting a roulette wheel. Equation (17) is used to define a source location, which is denoted by the letter a_{qy} after that; the new positions are derived by the use of Equation (18),

$$S_w = \frac{G_w/h_{xw}}{\sum_{y \in N_G} G_y/h_{xy}} \tag{17}$$

$$a_{xy}^{New} a_{xy} \varphi(a_{qy} a_{xy}) \tag{18}$$

It is extremely unlikely, but it is possible that there will be circumstances in which a solution with a higher rate will yield passive electro location. In order to circumvent this, Equation (19) has been calculated to select the following values for the parameters:

$$a_{xy}^{cand} \begin{cases} a_{xy}^{New} rand > F_x \\ a_{xy} otherwise \end{cases} \tag{19}$$

The final action taken by passive space is to alter one parameter as described by Equation (20) in order to increase the probability of a characteristic being exchanged,

$$a_{xy}^{cand} = a_{miny} + rand(a_{maxy} - a_{miny}) \quad (20)$$

The complexity of the proposed EFO algorithm is determined by these phases. The determination of complexity in the active and inactive phases mostly revolves around the calculation of distances between individuals. In the event that the value of the parameter number y goes above the allowed range, it will be recalculated according to the following constraints:

$$a_{xy}^{cand} = \begin{cases} a_{miny} & a_{xy}^{cand} < a_{miny} \\ a_{xy}^{cand} & a_{maxy} > a_{xy}^{cand} > a_{miny} \\ a_{maxy} & a_{xy}^{cand} > a_{maxy} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

3.4. SVM classifier

Support Vector Machines (SVM) stand out as a powerful and versatile classifier within the realm of machine learning. Their popularity stems from their ability to effectively handle a wide range of tasks due to their robust theoretical foundation. SVMs are rooted in statistical learning theory and optimization principles, providing a rigorous framework for their operation. This theoretical underpinning not only instills confidence in the reliability of SVMs but also contributes to their generalization performance across diverse datasets. One distinctive feature of SVMs is their ability to identify global optimal solutions, even when trained with a limited number of examples. This characteristic is particularly advantageous in real-world scenarios where obtaining an extensive labelled dataset may be challenging or costly. The use of a linear model in SVMs involves a transformative process, wherein non-linear mapping input vectors are elevated into a multi-dimensional space. This transformation enables the

creation of non-linear class borders, allowing SVMs to capture intricate relationships within the data. In the context of this multi-dimensional space, SVMs construct a hyperplane to achieve optimal separation between distinct decision classes. A key advantage of SVMs lies in their capability to identify optimal hyperplanes. These hyperplanes, constructed in the multi-dimensional space, serve as decisive boundaries, effectively separating different decision classes. This ability is particularly crucial in remote sensing images where clear delineation between classes is paramount, ensuring the accuracy and efficiency of the model.

4. Results and Discussion

The proposed detection model was trained on an NVIDIA GTX 1080Ti (12G) GPU. The training environment details includes a total of 500 training epochs were conducted with a batch size of 64, maximizing GPU utilization and matching the image resolution of the dataset. The initial learning rate was set to 0.01, with a weight decay of 0.0005. The images of the steel sheets are taken from the database "Severstal" for various types of lighting fixtures like LED, fluorescent and high discharge lamps. It includes, 1256 steel sheet images for training, 252 steel sheet images are used for testing and another 252 steel sheet images are used for validation of the proposed algorithm. An expert based decision is used to cross verify the classification efficiency of the proposed algorithm. Images of size 231x 229 are used for analysis. 80% of the images are used for training followed by 10% each for testing and validation. Effectiveness of defect detection is estimated using Multiple Image Classification Accuracy (MICA) as mentioned in Equation (22). The various types of flaws include, Map-Cracking, scratches, patches and surface pits are depicted in Table 1 with their respective values of MICA.

Table 1: Classification based on Categorization of Steel sheet defects using OCAFRN

Category	Training	Testing	Validation	%MICA _{train}	%MICA _{train}	%MICA _{val}
Total no. of defective steel sheets	1256	126	126	NA	NA	NA
Map-Cracking	314	32	32	98.4	98.3	98.3
Scratches	314	31	31	98.04	96.77	96.77
Patches	314	31	31	93.8	93.5	93.5
Surface Pits	314	31	31	98.4	98.3	98.3
Total no. of non-defective steel sheets	1256	126	126	99.9	99.2	99.2

Derived from the Northeastern University Surface Defect Dataset (NEU-DET), as depicted in Figure 3, the dataset employed in this research comprises a diversified range of defects including cracks, inclusions, and patches, surface dents, rolled scales and scratches with variation in light distribution patterns. The light distribution patterns are high bay lights, task lighting and linear luminaries. Each

defect category encompasses a total of 400 samples, resulting in a comprehensive set of 1200 grayscale images. The dimensions of each image measure 300 x 300 pixels, and it is noteworthy that a single image may exhibit multiple instances of defects.

Fig. 3: Steel sheets with various types of defects

$$\%MICA = 2 * |Reference Image \cap Test Image| / (|Reference Image| + |Test Image|) * 100 \tag{22}$$

4.1. Evaluation Metrics

In the task of object detection, Precision (P) and Recall (R) are commonly used to evaluate the performance of object detection models, while defect detection accuracy is employed to assess the overall model performance. Precision and Recall are calculated based on the confusion matrix, where each column represents the predicted class, and each row represents the true classification of the data. The elements in the confusion matrix are defined as follows:

TP (True Positive): The model correctly identifies positive samples.

FN (False Negative): The model fails to identify positive samples.

FP (False Positive): The model incorrectly identifies

negative samples as positive samples.

TN (True Negative): The model correctly identifies negative samples.

$$\text{Defect Detection Accuracy} = (TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN)$$

The loss function serves as a crucial component in the training of neural networks, quantifying the disparity between predicted and true values during the iteration. It plays a pivotal role in defining the training state of the model and guiding the optimization process towards improved performance. The loss function serves as a crucial component in the training of neural networks, quantifying the disparity between predicted and true values during the iteration. It plays a pivotal role in defining the training state of the model and guiding the optimization process towards improved performance. Figure 4 serves as a visual representation of the training process, showcasing the interplay between accuracy and the loss function over different epochs.

This graphical representation is instrumental in understanding how well the model evolves during the training phase. The values of the defect detection accuracy for training, testing and validation set offer insights into the convergence and generalization of the model and is illustrated in Table 2. The reduction in the training set loss function from 150% to 20% indicates a substantial improvement in the ability of the model to minimize errors on the data used for training purpose. Similarly, the validation set loss function decreasing from 150% to 20% suggests that the model is not over fitting and is capable of generalizing well to unseen data. In subsequent sections, the implications of these training process dynamics will be explored, shedding light on the robustness and effectiveness of the optimized cascaded CaffeNet region Network (OCAFRN) for defect detection during processing of steel sheets as in Figure 5.

Table 2: Analysis of the designed architectures for defect detection in Steel Sheets

Techniques Used	Architecture used	Defect Detection Accuracy (%)		
		Training	Testing	Validation
Feature Extraction	Faster RCNN	75%	76%	76%
	CAFFENET	88%	88%	81%
	OCAFRN	96%	96%	95%
	PCA	74%	75%	75%
	LDA	78%	79%	79%
Classification	R-CNN	96%	96%	95%
	HYBRID KNN (HKNN)	92%	94%	90%
	SVM	85%	86%	86%
	BPA	82%	84%	84%
	RBF	80%	79%	79%

Fig. 4: The Defect Detection Accuracy curve for training process

Fig. 5: Display of the Defective areas on the steel sheet surface

Scratches, dents, cracks, and corrosion some are examples of minor flaws that can arise during the manufacture of steel sheets. Table 1 shows that in order to find flaws in this work, we have taken into consideration the following defects: Map-Cracking, this is a sort of crack; Scratches; Patches; and Surface Pits (dents).

The absence of moisture content prevents steel sheets from rusting, since the flaw identification procedure in steel sheet production is an online, real-time industrial process and the manufacture of steel sheets occurs at a very high temperature. Therefore, the quality of fault identification is unaffected by atmospheric and corrosion variables. However, due to variations in light intensity, industrial illumination does have an impact on the quality of fault detection in steel sheets. By taking pictures of the steel sheets in different light distribution patterns that are appropriate for an industrial setting, this problem is resolved. Table 4 provides this information. Variations in daylight may occur, which could impact the quality of defect identification. Therefore, LED lighting fixtures with light distributions such as task lighting, high bay lights, and linear luminaries are utilized to offset the variation in daylight in order to maintain uniformity.

Types of lighting fixtures, light distribution, and

illumination-influencing factors are only a few of the variables that vary in industrial lighting. The energy efficiency, lifetime, and light quality of various lighting fixture types—including LEDs, fluorescent, and HID lights—vary. The way light is dispersed in an industrial location is also influenced by patterns of light distribution, such as Type III for roads or linear fixtures for wide regions. The total illumination levels and features of the lighting system can also be affected by variables including voltage fluctuations, the time of day, and the surrounding surroundings. Table 3 illustrates that usage of LED lighting will be suitable for steel manufacturing industries where the different types of defects are to be monitored and avoided.

Calculation for Defect Detection Accuracy for feature extraction from the images of steel sheets with cracks, inclusions, patches, surface dents, rolled scales and scratches is given below.

Training

RCNN (Training, Testing and Validation)

$$= (TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN) = (70+5)/(70+5+15+10) = 75\%$$

$$\text{CAFFENET} = (87+1)/(87+1+10+2) = 88\%$$

$$\text{OCAFRN} = (95+1)/(95+2+2+1)=96\%$$

Testing

RCNN (Training, Testing and Validation)

$$= (TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN) = (37+1)/(37+1+6+6) = 76\%$$

$$\text{CAFFENET} = (43+1)/(43+1+3+3) = 88\%$$

$$\text{OCAFRN} = (47+1)/(47+1+1+1)=96\%$$

Validation

RCNN (Training, Testing and Validation)

$$= (TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN) = (15+1)/(15+1+3+2) = 76\%$$

$$\text{CAFFENET} = (16+1)/(16+1+2+2) = 81\%$$

$$\text{OCAFRN} = (19+1)/(19+1+0+1)=95\%$$

Training

CNN (Training, Testing and Validation)

$$= (TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN) = (80+5)/(80+5+10+5) = 85\%$$

$$\text{HYBRID KNN} = (91+1)/(91+1+4+4) = 92\%$$

$$\text{SVM} = (95+1)/(95+2+2+1)=96\%$$

Testing

CNN (Training, Testing and Validation) =

$$(TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN) = (42+1)/(42+1+4+3) = 86\%$$

$$\text{HYBRID KNN} = (46+1)/(46+1+1+2) = 94\%$$

$$\text{SVM} = (47+1)/(47+1+1+1)=96\%$$

Validation

CNN (Training, Testing and Validation) =

$$(TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN) = (17+1)/(17+1+1+2) = 86\%$$

$$\text{HYBRID KNN} = (18+1)/(18+1+1+1) = 90\%$$

$$\text{SVM} = (19+1)/(19+1+0+1)=95\%$$

Table 3: Classification of Steel sheet defects due to variation in Lighting Fixtures type

Category	Faster RCNN	OCAFRN	CAFFENE T	PCA	LDA	SVM	H KNN	R-CNN	BPA	RB F
Lighting Fixture type - LED										
Map-Cracking	98.3	98.4	98.3	79.3	78.4	89.3	92.3	96.4	82.3	80.3
Scratches	96.77	98.04	96.77	71.77	77.04	87.77	94.77	96.04	81.7	79.7
Patches	93.5	93.8	93.5	71.5	76.8	89.5	91.5	95.8	81.5	79.5
Surface Pits	98.3	98.4	98.3	73.3	78.4	89.3	90.3	95.4	80.3	79.3
Lighting Fixture type -Fluorescent										
Map-Cracking	97.3	97.4	97.3	78.3	77.4	85.3	91.3	95.4	81.3	78.3
Scratches	95.77	97.04	95.77	71.5	76.04	86.77	93.77	95.04	80.7	77.7
Patches	92.5	92.8	92.5	71.4	75.8	87.5	90.5	94.8	80.5	77.5
Surface Pits	97.3	97.4	97.3	73.6	76.4	88.3	89.3	94.4	79.3	77.3
Lighting Fixture type - High-Intensity Discharge										
Map-Cracking	96.3	96.4	96.3	77.3	75.4	84.3	90.3	92.4	80.3	77.3
Scratches	94.77	96.04	96.77	70.5	74.04	85.7	89.77	91.04	78.7	76.7
Patches	91.5	91.8	91.5	70	73.8	86.5	89.5	92.8	78.5	76.5
Surface Pits	96.3	96.4	96.3	72.6	73.4	87.3	88.3	92.4	77.3	75.3

Table 4: Classification of Steel sheet defects due to variation in Light Distribution Patterns

Category	Faster RCNN	OCAFRN	CAFFENE T	PCA	LDA	SVM	H KNN	R-CNN	BPA	RB F
Light Distribution - Linear luminaries										
Map-Cracking	98.23	98.33	98.31	79.34	78.41	89.33	92.33	96.42	82.2	80.5
Scratches	96.76	98.2	96.76	71.77	77.04	87.77	94.77	96.04	81.6	79.6
Patches	93.52	93.7	93.51	71.51	76.82	89.51	91.52	95.81	81.7	79.4
Surface Pits	98.31	98.6	98.32	73.32	78.41	89.32	90.32	95.41	80.5	79.5
Light Distribution - High bay lights										
Map-Cracking	98.36	98.36	98.23	79.41	78.51	89.43	92.46	96.32	82.2	80.4
Scratches	96.66	98.22	96.27	71.57	77.24	87.57	94.47	96.14	81.5	79.5
Patches	93.42	93.72	93.35	71.61	76.72	89.58	91.42	95.71	81.6	79.6
Surface Pits	98.34	98.56	98.52	73.62	78.52	89.11	90.43	95.32	80.4	79.2
Light Distribution - Task lighting										
Map-Cracking	98.13	98.24	98.33	79.43	78.5	89.63	92.73	96.14	82.1	80.6
Scratches	96.17	98.24	96.37	71.47	77.54	87.67	94.77	96.14	81.2	79.7
Patches	93.15	93.28	93.35	71.45	76.58	89.65	91.75	95.28	81.4	79.8
Surface Pits	98.13	98.24	98.36	73.43	78.54	89.63	90.73	95.24	80.5	79.6

Table 5: Classification of Steel sheet defects due to various factors affecting Illumination

Category	Faster RCNN	OCAFRN	CAFFENE T	PCA	LDA	SVM	H KNN	R-CNN	BPA	RB F
Time of day and weather										
Map-Cracking	98.23	98.64	98.31	79.31	78.14	89.23	92.38	96.41	82.5	80.6
Scratches	96.37	98.74	96.27	71.72	77.24	87.37	94.87	96.03	81.6	79.8
Patches	93.45	93.88	93.45	71.54	76.68	89.45	91.65	95.28	81.6	79.6
Surface Pits	98.53	98.54	98.43	73.33	78.54	89.53	90.43	95.34	80.4	79.7

Linear luminaries are perfect for expansive spaces, such as manufacturing areas, as it offers uniform lighting throughout. High bay lights are designed to provide effective and targeted light distribution in industries and warehouses where the ceilings are very high. Task lighting enhances the visibility and safety in regions with a variety of operations by providing targeted illumination for particular tasks. As a result, it is inferred to use a

combination of linear luminaries, high bay lights and task lighting in steel manufacturing industries. Table 3, depicts that the OCAFRN model performs effectively as compared with other models for the three different types of light distributions that are prevalent in the steel factory environment. The two major factors that may affect the level of illumination includes the time of the day for a particular weather and environmental factors like rust, dust

and temperature. The visibility can be enhanced by influencing the level of illumination needed and also recommended for multiple lighting distribution patterns as per the need. It is inferred from Table 4 that OCAFRN model performs well as compared with other models for any time period in a day, irrespective of the weather conditions. Since the defect detection on the surface of the steel sheets is carried out during the manufacturing process, the chance of rusting is eliminated. The only environmental factor that may affect the detection of defects on steel sheets during the manufacturing process is the lighting conditions which may vary with the time of the day for various weather conditions. This problem is also alleviated by using enhanced illumination schemes. Hence, a same result as in Table 4 is obtained and is recorded in Table 5.

5. Conclusion

In the domain of steel surface defect detection, addressing challenges posed by complex backgrounds and low-resolution datasets, this study introduces the OCAFRN model. In this work, four types of manufacturing defects are considered for analysis. LED lightings are a popular option in contemporary to industrial settings because of their great energy economy, long lifespan, and customizable light quality. Since the steel sheet processing industries are constructed on a huge land area with high ceiling, various light distribution patterns like linear luminaries, high bay light and task lighting are best suited for detecting the various types of flaws on the steel sheets by the proposed OCAFRN model. Integrating OCAFRN as the amalgamating network with R-CNN and SVM, the feature extraction and classification of the network is refined for low-resolution images. Special attention is strategically incorporated to mitigate issues like missed detections and imprecise localization in intricate backgrounds. Notably, the proposed model not only maintains a low parameter count but also outperforms other algorithms, particularly the BPA and RBF models, achieving superior values of Defect Detection Accuracy for various methods of feature extraction and classification. Thus, the algorithm excels in accurately identifying positions and contours of target defects, as evidenced by comprehensive experiments on complex backgrounds and low-resolution datasets of steel surface defects. As a future direction, to enhance the defect detection performance, it is proposed to use Cascaded Convolutional Neural Networks and include some more rare type of defect (lamination, center bursts and clinks) detection.

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